

**Developing metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen science
impacts on the environment and society**

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**Guidance for empirical research to inform
the design of the MICS toolbox and platform**

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Document Information

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2020_01_20	Uta Wehn	IHE Delft	Reference document from WP2 interview guidance.
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1 Background and purpose of this document

The MICS project aims to develop tools and methods for measuring the impacts of Citizen Science projects. WP3 “*Toolboxes for methods application, information visualisation, and delivery*” is responsible for developing the MICS toolbox, and aims to implement the impact-assessment indicators developed by WP2 “*Methods for measuring citizen science impact*”.

To this end, activities of WP3 will be:

- to conduct in-depth interviews with potential end-users of the MICS tools to understand their requirements.
- to maintain an ongoing communication with these end-users
- to understand their needs in terms of what MICS produces from the data they input

The resulting insights will feed into the development and design of the MICS toolbox.

This document has two purposes explains how interviews with potential end-users should be implemented, to ensure consistency regardless of which MICS partner undertakes an interview.

2 Guidance for semi-structured interviews on User Profile

The envisaged outcomes of the interviews are:

- To obtain insights into the user profile (user jobs, pains and gains) of potential future users of the MICS toolbox.
- To increase the interest and engagement of potential future users of the MICS toolbox and grow the interested MICS stakeholder community.

Each interview is expected to last up to 60 minutes.

The guidelines provided here detail the activities that the MICS *interviewers* (i.e. staff of MICS partners) need to undertake in the phase before the interview takes place, during its implementation and immediately following the interview.

2.1 Before the interview

Before the interview, the interviewer should complete the following actions:

- Familiarise yourself with the interview protocol (see next section)
- Arrange a time for the interview to be held. Also share with the interviewee:
 - A high level summary of the topics which will be discussed in the interview (but not detailed questions prompts).
 - The logistics of the interview including how long it will take, how the information will be used, how they can continue to be involved following the interview
 - A copy of the MICS informed consent sheet for them to fill out, tailored to the interview setting.
- The interviewer should also have a saved/printed copy of the interview protocol where they can make notes during the conversation (not for the interviewee).

2.2 During the interview

The interview will follow the main structure outlined below (see Table).

Interview structure	Purpose & approach
Welcome and introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Briefly introduce the MICS project; - explain objectives and structure of the interview; - double-check you have received a signed copy of the informed consent sheet - explain that data from the interview will be analysed and aggregated with other data and would be anonymised if shared publicly. - explain that the results of the study will also be shared with the respondent organization in due time - make clear that the interviewee can withdraw from the interview and/or the study at any stage by contacting micsprivacy@earthwatch.org.uk
Content-related questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interviewer asks the interview questions (see interview protocol) to obtain detailed insights; - Interviewee responds as preferred (incl. skipping questions)
Closing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thank the interviewee for their time; - explain next steps for MICS; - ask for interest in follow up, newsletter, report etc.

The interview will take place online (Skype or GoToMeeting). The interviewer should ask permission to type up notes during the interview, as some interviewees may find the sound of typing distracting. It can be hard to engage in a discussion whilst also taking notes so, if resources allow, two interviewers can be present- one to conduct the interview and the other to take notes.

If it is not possible to have two interviewers present a recording or automatic transcription can be taken. A recording can be done only with the explicit consent of the interviewee (note that recording the interview may be a deterrent for some interviewees, resulting in limited answers). However, it is strongly recommended NOT to rely exclusively on the recording (in case it fails), so please be sure to take notes. In general, creating a full transcript of the interview will not be necessary. Whilst it might be interesting to analyse this volume of information, it is not required to inform the user profile and would be very time consuming.

The interview protocol in Section 2.5 provides the guiding questions and prompts for the semi-structured interview.

- Given the semi-structured interview approach, the content-related questions (and prompts) are intended to trigger a meaningful discussion, the results of which can be compared across different interviews.
- The main questions should be asked and the interviewee should be given the chance to respond. Once they have answered the interviewer can follow up with the bulleted prompts and list of example answers (below each question). If the interviewee is struggling to answer a question the list of example answers can be used to help them think about their answer.
- Ideally, all the questions included in this protocol should be posed (and answered).

2.3 After the interview

- Transcribe the interview as soon as possible following the interview (ideally on the same day), turning your notes into full sentences and elaborations (incl. your own observations or comments) based on your full recollection of the interview.
- Update the list of example answers below each question if there were any new suggestions from the interviewee

2.4 Interview protocol

Interview protocol (pre-fill before interview)

Date of interview:

Start time:

End time:

Location of interview:

Name of interviewer:

Organisation of interviewer:

Welcome & introduction (5 minutes)

Purpose of the interview:

- To obtain insights into the existing needs of Project Coordinators in terms of measuring impact that can inform the design on the MICS platform
- To extend the interested MICS stakeholder community and potential future users of the MICS toolbox

We would like to ask you a series of questions – likely to last no longer than 1 hour - focusing on the following three themes:

1. How you personally think about, or refer to “impact” within your project
2. Methods for measuring impact; including those you have heard of, or have actually utilised yourself
3. How a novel tool for measuring impact may be beneficial to you as a project coordinator

What MICS will do with the obtained information:

- From these interviews and other activities, MICS will produce a summary of the user requirements for the MICS platform. This will be used to inform the design of the online toolbox for Citizen Science projects, so that they can easily measure the (evolving) impacts of their project/initiative.

IMPORTANT: make sure you have received a signed copy of the MICS Informed Consent sheet.

Project-related Questions (30 minutes- approx. 3 minutes per question)

1. In MICS we talk about “impact” of a project to refer to “changes” caused by that project, but in other projects you may use a different terminology for this concept, for example terms such

as Outcomes or Results. What term do you use to refer to “changes” caused by your project?
(please specify)

- a. How do you use the term impact in your project? Do you have a definition?
2. We assume you’re interested in measuring impact. Have you tried to measure impact in your project before? – **Yes/No**

If “yes”

- a) For what purpose did you measure impact? **Reporting purposes / Project-proposal preparation / Accounting purposes / Learning / promotion for project partners / Other (please specify)**
- b) How did you measure impact? Did you use an existing method? – **Yes, published method (please expand about the method used, where possible) / Yes, developed in-house / No specific method used / other (please specify)**
 - i) Did you read any literature beforehand? **Yes / No**
 - ii) If “no”, what puts you off using a method for measuring impact? **Not aware of them / too tricky / takes too much time / uncertain of quality or accuracy / focuses on wrong parameters / not a project priority / other (please specify)**
- c) Did you feel it produced a good representation of your project’s impact? **Yes/No**
- d) What factors/indicators did you measure?: **Data points collected / citizens involved / space covered / time taken / money spent / papers published / attitudes changed / policies changed / different audiences engaged / quality of data / uptake in media / other (please specify)**
- e) What additional factors/indicators would you have liked to consider? **Policy influence / attitudes changed / education / benefits to participants / RRI (hard to measure MoRRI) / capture the unexpected impacts / other (please specify)**
- f) What were the challenges in measuring your projects impact? **Factors/Indicators not clearly defined / time consuming / expensive / time and effort required from participants / different geographic scale of impact / Impact continues to occur after the project / other (please specify)**
 - i) What were the specific challenges for each factor/indicator you measured?
- g) When did you measure impact? **Before the project (assessment during project-proposal preparation) / frequently / end of project only / other (please specify)**
 - (i) How much time did you spend assessing impact? – **Impossible to assess / Hours / Days / Weeks**
 - (ii) Was the time you spent measuring impact worth it? Why?

If “no”

- h) Can you explain why you haven’t tried to measure impact? **Takes a lot of time / requires substantial effort / don’t have the knowledge / don’t know which method to use / not a project priority / other (please specify)**
- 4) What would be the consequences for your project of not being able to measure impact?
 - a) What would be the consequences for your project of not being confident in your assessment of impact?
 - b) What would be the consequences for your project of being able to successfully measure impact?

- 5) Who is actually interested in the impact of your project? – **nobody / project funder / citizen scientists / policy makers / other researchers / citizen science community / industry / other (please specify)**
- a) Who, including yourself, is most interested in the impact of your project?

General Impact Questions (20 minutes- approx. 2-3 minutes per question)

- 5) Have you seen any examples of good impact measurement? **Yes / No**
- a) Have you seen any examples of bad impact measurement? **Yes / No**
- b) Can you describe them? What were they like?
- 6) What made you agree to volunteer to discuss the MICS tools? **I know something about impact / I want my project to be among the first ones featured in the MICS platform / I don't want to be left out of the Impact party / learning more about impact / reflect on how well you're doing / other (please specify)**
- 7) What were/are you hoping the MICS tools can help you with? **Accurate method of measuring impact / Objectivity in impact assessment / Access to experts in the field of impact / Keep up to date with developments / Accessible way to measure impact for non-experts / Learn something about impact / A common framework for impact measurement / compare your performance with others / other (please specify)**
- 8) Now that you thought more about all this, consider again in which situations would a tool to measure the impact of your project be helpful to you? **Project-proposal preparation / design of the project / during the project / reporting to a funder / reporting to participants / internal reporting / communications material / for your own interest / other (please specify).**
- a) Which would be the most important for you, if any?
- 9) Which features would be most important for you in a platform which measures impact? **Good design / guarantee of measurements / endorsement by funder (for example the European Commission), ECSA/CSA/ACSA / endorsement by other projects / other (please specify)**
- 10) Impact is change relative to something. What would you want the impact of your project measured in relation to? **Project vs absence of the project (counter factual) / citizen science vs traditional science / project vs other projects / resources used in the project vs resources used in another way / other (please specify)**
- 11) Would you be interested in comparing the impact of your project with other projects? **Yes/No**
- 12) What do you think a good impact assessment output would look like? **A score out of 10 / a story or case study / a colour scale (red, amber, green) / raw data (CSV file) available / a map / other (please specify)**

Closing (5 minutes)

Explanation of the next steps

- All results from interviews will be analysed.
- MICS will produce an online toolbox for Citizen Science projects to measure the (evolving) impacts of their project/initiative
- We will invite you to test the tools and give feedback

Those are all the questions that we wanted to ask. Thank you for your time!